

A Narrative of Visually Impaired Person through Study and Career in Nepal

Laxmi Prasad Bhandari

PhD Scholar, Graduate School of Education Tribhuvan University, Kathmandu Nepal

ABSTRACT

The teaching learning strategy for visually impaired students, whether they should be taught in common classroom or in a separate classroom, is a debate in education. This is a narrative study related to that debate. The main objective of this study is to find out the suitable teaching- learning activities for visually impaired from the perception of such children and their teacher. The participant of this study was a visually impaired person who was selected using purposive sampling procedure. He had the study experience in a separate classroom and common classrooms both. He studied first two Grades in separate classrooms for visually impaired and Grade three to bachelor's level in common classrooms. After completing a bachelor's level in English, he has worked as a teacher for visually impaired children for four years and for all types of children for three years. This study is conducted in Panchthar district of eastern Nepal. One in-depth interview following by a series of short telephone interviews and observation were used as data collection techniques. It is concluded that special needs children should be taught in a separate classroom for learning of basic skills of reading and writing and then they must be taught in an inclusive classroom with other students for greater learning achievements. By managing the modern equipment of information communication technology for visually impaired children, the inclusive classroom can be used from the beginning of formal education.

KEYWORDS: Special needs children; separate classroom; common or inclusive classroom; visually impaired; braille.

ARTICLE DETAILS

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INTRODUCTION

A child means a minor who has not attained eighteen years of age (The National Civil Code Act, 2017). Every child shall have the right to education, health, maintenance, proper care, sports, entertainment, and overall personality development from the families and the state (Constitution of Nepal, 2015).

A child is any person under the age of eighteen, unless national laws specify an earlier age of majority. Children must have their civil, political, economic, social, health, and cultural rights (UNO, 1989). On November 20, 1989, the Convention on the Rights of the Child was approved by the UN general assembly and made available for signatures.

Children are future citizens of a country. So, every child has got the right to live a life, the opportunity to develop his/her personality, the opportunity to read and write, the opportunity to proper health service, and security. Thus, various needs that are compulsory for children are called children's rights. Under child rights, the right to live, the right to development, the right to protection, and the right to participation are included (MOECD, 2015).

According to the population census of 2011 of Nepal, the total population reported to have some kind of disability is 513,321, which is 1.94 % of the total population (26,494,504) of the country. Out of total disabled persons, 18.5% have blindness/low vision or 94,765 people have blindness or low vision (CBS, 2012, p.211). In Panchthar district, 816 people (male 380 and female 436) have blindness or low vision (ibid, p.215).

"International Human Rights treaties prohibit any exclusion from or limitation to educational opportunities on the basis of socially ascribed or perceived differences. They included differences in "sex," "race," "ethnic," "origin," "language," religion," "political or other opinions," "national origin," "birth," "descent," "economic condition," "property," "social origin," "disability" and "the status activities expressed opinions or beliefs of the child's parent's, legal guardians or the family members" (UNESCO, 2012, p.4).

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The term "special needs" in the UK typically refers to special requirements in an educational setting. Special education needs (SEN) or special education needs and disabilities (SEND) are other names for this. As of 2005, more than 13.5 million children in the United States, or 18.5% of all children under the age of 18, had special health care needs (Cunningham, 2005 as cited in en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/special-needs).

A child with special needs is a young person who has been identified as needing certain care and requirements that other children do not. In order to provide benefits and support for the child's development and well-being, the state may designate this status. Additionally, special needs may be legally designated, especially in the context of adoption and foster care, when the child and guardian get support to help them both lead productive lives (Kagan, 2020).

In many developing countries, the past few decades have witnessed a debate on inclusive education. The debate is whether the education of special needs children should be managed in the same school and the same classroom with other students or not. Two types of voices can be seen about the issue.

Some voices are supporting inclusive education or they are arguing that education must be provided to special needs children in the same classroom with other students.

Stainback and Stainback (1991) argued that inclusive education is the most effective means of combating discriminatory attitudes, creating welcoming communities, building an inclusive society, and equal educational opportunities for all (as cited in Aremu and Olufemi, 2009).

Inclusion is currently considered a 'process involved in making mainstream schools accessible in terms of curriculum and teaching, organization, management, the physical environment, ethos and culture' (Swain and Cook 2001: 186 as cited in Ypinazar and Pagliano, 2004: 439).

Inclusion responds to individual differences, benefits all learners, changes attitudes towards diversity, is foundational to a just, non-discriminatory society and is cost-effective as all children are served in one pedagogical setting (Ballard 2012; Deppeler 2006; Biesta and Tedder 2007; Flecha and Soler 2013; Florian 2012 as cited in Majoko, 2017)

Not only the special needs children but other children also can be benefited from the inclusive classroom. Several benefits of inclusion to children without disabilities including the development of empathy, compassion, tolerance, and realization of their capabilities (Chireshe 2013; Idol 2006; Kisanji and Saanane 2009; Majoko 2017; Rafferty and Griffin 2005 as cited in Majoko, 2017).

There is confusion with inclusion whether inclusion is a means to an end or an end itself. The supporters of full inclusion argued that "separate special needs placement is wrong because a key goal of education should be to fully include children in the community in which they live. Therefore, they ought to be included in their local mainstream schools" (Warnock, 2005 as cited in Hornby, 2011 p. 327). However, "inclusion in the community after leaving school is actually the most important end that educators should be seeking. Inclusion in mainstream schools may be a means to that end but should not be an end in itself" (ibid).

On the other hand, some voices are different than this argument. They had presented their idea that 'full inclusion' with its vision of all children being educated in mainstream classrooms, for all or most of their time at school is impossible to achieve in practice. This is because it is considered that there will always be some children with special education needs and disabilities who cannot be successfully included in mainstream classrooms, which sets a limit to the proportion of children who can be effectively educated in mainstream schools (Evans and Lunt, 2002; Kaufman and Badar, 2014; Thomas and Loxley, 2007 as cited in Hornby, 2015 p. 236).

Research suggests that many students with disabilities (SWD) will not be able to advance along with grade-level academic standards with the instruction typically provided in the regular classroom even with accommodation and supports (Gilmour, 2018).

Gilmour (2018) citing Fuchs et al. (2015) compared the size of the math achievement gap between students with or at risk for learning disabilities and their non-disabled peers. SWDs randomly assigned to two groups. In the first one, students with or at risk for disabilities received intensive fractions instructions, exemplifying special education techniques, while those in the second group were exposed to fractions instruction in the regular classroom with accommodation based on the principles of universal design for learning (that is, instruction that includes multiple means for students to express what they know). The math achievement gap between students with or at risk for disabilities and without disabilities in the regular classroom setting was twice as large as the gap in the first group.

Educational programs for student with disabilities have traditionally been built upon the assumption that a variety of service delivery options needs to be available. Special education law, for example, stipulates that schools place students with disabilities in the least restrictive environment. The notion of least restrictive environment as that there are alternatives along a continuum of restrictiveness with residential institutions on the end of the continuum and regular classes on the other (Hallahan & Kauffman, 1998 as cited in Fakolade, Adeniyi, and Tella, 2009).

The inclusion of children with disabilities into general classroom affects the time spent on instruction as well as the time spent on classroom management by teachers. The teacher has to spend more time on classroom management for the class which has a large percentage of students with special needs. So, she/he can spend less time only on instruction. On the other hand, the teacher can spend more time on instruction for the class which has a small percentage of students with special needs because the time required for classroom management in such classes is less (Cooc, 2019).

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Technology can play a positive role in the lives of persons with disabilities. It can support the learning of visually impaired students. It has impacted positively on the lives of persons with disabilities concerning information use, education, and lifelong learning. It would not only expand the world of the visually impaired students, but it can also serve as a great equalizer (Olukotun, 2004 as cited in Eligi and Mwantimwa, 2017).

In Nepal, there are two types of practices. The first is, there are special education classes managed in community schools where special needs children are taught in separate classrooms. For example, the special education classes for the students not having visual capacity, the special education classes for students not having hearing capacity, etc. The second is, teaching special needs children in common classrooms with other general children.

In most of the schools having separate classrooms managed for special needs children and performing separate teaching-learning activities from grades 1 to 2, the students have to go to the common classrooms of other students for the education of grades 3 to 12. In Panchthar district of eastern Nepal, three secondary schools have special education classes and out of them, one school is having classes for visually impaired. In that school, visually impaired students are being taught from Grade one up to Grade four in separate classroom now. These students have to go to common classrooms in grade five and they have to get an education there up to grade 12.

After 12 also, they have to study in common classes for university education.

The theory of inclusion is an important theoretical base in this matter. According to this theory, inclusion is "a process that helps to overcome barriers limiting the presence, participation, and achievement of learners" (UNESCO, 2017, p.7).

The visually impaired children are facing difficulties in learning. In various places, they are deprived of getting the opportunity of education. Inclusive education is the process of strengthening the capacity of the education system to reach out to all learners. The theory of inclusion have focused on inclusive education.

In this context, some education and classroom-related questions have also been brought to the fore. The following are the research questions:

- a. How is there inclusion or exclusion in learning, looking at the overall condition of the visually impaired children?
- b. How the inclusion of visually impaired students is managed in the local mainstream schools of Nepal?
- c. Which type of teaching-learning activities will be better? Either special education having separate classrooms for visually impaired children or performing teaching-learning activities in common classes with other children and how?
- d. How are the teacher and students experiencing and viewing this issue?

The article is significant because such issues lie at the heart of the existing educational debate. The study contributes partially to this debate and discusses how visually impaired children/students experience the learning practices. It also contributes to the discourse about the teacher's views who are teaching visually impaired children/students. The study shows the reality of teaching learning environment for visually impaired students and it suggests the ways to increase learning achievement for such students which can provide guidance to policy makers and implementers. Therefore it will contribute in inclusion process.

METHODOLOGY

I have used the narrative research design in this study. The participant in my study was a man- 'Kailash' who was selected by purposive sampling (his real name has been changed to protect his anonymity). He was visually impaired. His birthplace was Hilihang rural municipality of Panchthar district. I used interview guidelines and observation as tools for data collection.

During my focused in-depth interview with Kailash, I tried to maintain the natural environment. I took permission from him and used my mobile phone to record the interview. I transcribed the in-depth interview and drew insights from those transcriptions. Then again, I have conducted a series of short telephone interviews for the clarification of insights received from the in-depth interview. After clarification of such insights, I drew themes and used such themes in the narrative. I used observation for collecting information about the overall household condition of Kailash and used observation notes to list the information. The information received from observation provided support to complete the study. I tried to maintain the researcher's ethical code of conduct and did not conceal the fact that his story would constitute a part of my study. I also assured that his right to anonymity and privacy would be protected by not disclosing his identity in my written works. In this way, I was able to collect rich narrative data from him, which enabled me to explain the problem faced by visually impaired students in Nepali schools.

I was guided by the theory of inclusion in education when doing this study. During this narrative study, I have tried to pay attention to the presence, participation, and achievement of a visually impaired child in the education system.

Being visually impaired is also a kind of disability. So, limitation to the proper educational opportunity for a visually impaired child is also a kind of exclusion. If the state cannot provide the proper educational opportunity to the special needs children, it means there is an exclusion in the education system.

Kailash, born at Hilihang rural municipality in Panchthar district, was visually impaired at the time of his birth. But his family members, even his mother had not known that fact till he attended the age of 5 months. After his age of 5 months, they saw he was not looking straight on anything but looking diagonal. He could not play with toys also. Then his mother and other family

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members found that he had no eyesight.

At the time of his birth, his father was in Dubai for foreign employment. Kailash was born at his mother's parent's home. Kailash was the fourth fetus of his mother. His mother returned her home from her parent's home when Kailash was 2 years of age. She came with small child Kailash. She had done food farming and animal husbandry alone. His father came from Dubai when Kailash was of 7 years. Kailash's father had not any idea whether he has to send his son to school or not. Kailash went to nearby school himself with his playing friends but the school denied to admit him. The school authority said that Kailash can't write and the written exam can't be possible. Despite visually impaired, Kailash went to school regularly without admission. He was a clever boy. He could not write because of the lack of eyesight, but he could tell all the poems and lessons of Nepali and even the multiplication tables of mathematics.

Just after some time, the classes for visually impaired started at Phidim, the head quarter of the Panchthar district, and his father got the information of that class. He brought his son to that school and admitted him. Kailash studied at the separate classroom up to grade two with his visually impaired friends. Then, he joined a common classroom with other friends in grade three. He studied in the common classroom up to grade 8 in that school. He went to another school in grade 9 because the previous school was up to grade 8 only. Kailash was admitted to that school in grade 9 and studied there up to grade 12. He was a clever student in the class from the early grades. In SLC and higher secondary exams, he got success in the first division. He had got admitted to a nearby college and completed the bachelor's level in English and English education both. Even at the bachelor's level, he was the class topper. The school where he had studied up to grade 8 demanded a teacher for visually impaired students. Kailash applied for that post. He was selected from the competitors and he is an ideal teacher now. He is now studying the master's degree in education planning and management also. Kailash is my student at the master's level and I had taught him from grade 9 to grade 12 also at his school time. Therefore I had a good opportunity to develop a rapport with him, his father, mother, and sisters. I have made several informal conversations with Kailash when he was at the secondary and higher secondary level. He and his father had come to my house many times. I had also gone to his house many times.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This narrative study is related to problems and struggles of visually impaired children for education. Therefore the key findings of the problems and struggles of such types of children are discussed below, for which I have tried to make a linkage of discussion with the theory of inclusion and the concepts provided by UNESCO. The following sections illustrate how visually impaired children are facing problems and struggles and what are their effects on inclusion.

Exclusion in learning

Visually impaired children face problems in maintaining life prospects needed for learning. Most such children in rural areas have to be suffered by the inadequate facility of food, housing, clothing, limited security, and safety, etc. This can be the cause of the exclusion of children from learning. In response to the question "How have your childhood passed?" Kailash shared his experience to this regard as:

My daddy went to Dubai for foreign employment leaving my mummy at her parent's home. I was born there and we were there till two years after my birth. Then she brought me to our own small home, made by my daddy which was in the next village. Mummy had done food farming and animal husbandry alone at that time. On the other hand, I was visually impaired. My mother had to face several problems. My childhood is full of misery.

Children are the base for the future development of the country. Therefore, it is the responsibility of the state to maintain life prospects for learning to every child of the country. If any child is facing the problem of proper nutrition, clothing, housing, etc. there can't be a suitable condition for learning. For visually impaired children, it relates to the right to social security also. Kailash had faced several such problems. Being his father abroad for foreign employment and compulsion of managing all household and agricultural works by his mother alone, the life prospects needed for learning could not be maintained. It made the condition of exclusion in learning. UNESCO (2012) has clearly stated that the problems in having the life prospects needed for learning can be noted as a type of exclusion. I have made a connection to the childhood situation of Kailash to this concept of UNESCO and concluded that Kailash faced a kind of exclusion in learning.

If the teaching-learning activities are not managed according to the needs of children or the teaching-learning process can't meet the learning need of a learner, there can't be meaningful learning. Lack of meaningful learning indirectly restricts inclusion or promotes exclusion.

Kailash had experienced such matters.

Answering my question "Did you have sufficient learning materials at that time?" He said:

At that time, only one teacher (ma'am) was there at school for teaching us. She taught us alone up to grade 2. We had only one stylus (writing pen) and only one slate (writing plate). She taught us to write by using that stylus and slate turn by turn. At greater grades also, we had a lack of brail books and other necessary materials.

Meaningful learning cannot be possible if there is a lack of teachers and learning materials. Kailash and his visually impaired friends have faced this type of problem. The writing practices using only one stylus and one slate by ten students and only

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one teacher for visually impaired students of many grades were not sufficient for the meaningful learning experience. In that situation, the teaching-learning process and instruction technique are not corresponding to the learning styles of the learner.

As UNESCO (2012) had stated if the learning materials are not sufficiently managed or the learner feels uncomfortable in learning or the learner has discouraging experience at school or college that can be called exclusion from the meaningful learning experience. The overall condition of educational management in Kailash's classroom in the preliminary grades exactly matches to the above concept of UNESCO. This also proves a kind of exclusion from meaningful learning. This shows that the visually impaired children were excluded from the meaningful learning experience.

Denial of admission at school

Most of the special needs children including visually impaired children in Nepal have no opportunity to be admitted to nearby schools in the preliminary grades. The government has managed special education classes for visually impaired in a few places only. The general basic schools hesitate to take the admission for such children. Most of their guardians have either inadequate awareness or they can't search the educational institution for their special needs children far from their residence. I asked him "Was the school positive to admit you in the beginning where you wanted to study?"

He answered:

I went to school which is near my house with my playing friends. I heard their readings and pronunciation and I learned. I had the knowledge of whole lessons and I could tell the whole lessons of Nepali but could not write because I had not any eyesight. The poems of Nepali and the multiplication chart of mathematics were in my mouth. Despite having all this information, the school denied taking admission because the problem was neither there could be the possibility of operating a written exam for me nor upgrading me in the upper class. They said to my father that the written exam was compulsory for evaluation and I was unable for that. Although the school was near my house, I went there for one year without admission just for listening to the readings of friends

The visually impaired children have to learn to write in brail script in the beginning phase of formal education. For teaching such children in general school, teacher training must be provided and teaching-learning materials must be managed as per the needs of such children. If such management is not available, the school has to face problems in teaching them. For that reason, the schools hesitate to admit them. On the other hand, the school has to conduct the written exam for promotion to upper grades, and for that purpose, the writing capacity is necessary for visually impaired children. Kailash went to a nearby school with his father. They requested the school administration for admission. Neither the teachers were able to teach in brail script, nor the learning materials like brail book, stylus, and slate were available with them.

The voice of Kailash shows that because of a few schools having managed classrooms, teaching-learning materials and the teachers for special needs children, they are being excluded from entry in the nearby school or an educational program.

Hornby (2011) citing Warnock (2005) had said the main goal of education should fully include children in the community in which they lived. If they are included in their local mainstream schools, inclusion in the community after leaving school will be comparatively easier. But the denial of admission at local mainstream school for Kailash became a problem on one side and the lack of learning materials and teachers on his admitted school at district headquarter on the other side were challenges for inclusion. Anyway, Kailash completed his school education facing various problems.

Misbehavior at school

The society has to give appropriate value for learning acquired by visually impaired children. If learning acquired by them is considered to be of little value by society or if they feel disrespected or misbehaved at school and workplaces or limited work opportunities are available to the area of learning acquired, in general, that is called exclusion from contributing the learning acquired to the development of community and society.

My participant Kailash is a teacher in that school where he had got his education from grade one up to grade eight. He teaches special needs classes as well as general classes.

I asked him "Do you have any experience of misbehavior done by other friends for the visually impaired person like you?" He expresses his experience in this regard:

Fortunately, I had not felt bad treatment from other friends to me when I was a student. But I have heard that some special needs children have to be humiliated or insulted by others in some places.

His interpretation shows that there is a bad treatment to the special needs children in some places.

In answering my question, "How was your feeling for selection as a teacher in self-studied school?" Kailash expressed the feeling of happiness and proud of his selection as a teacher as:

I felt so much happy when I was selected as a teacher in that school where I had studied. I made a phone call to daddy and I talk to daddy and mummy both. They became happy. They had tension about whether their son can get the job or not. I had got the job.

I put my curiosity with him "How do your general students behave you as their teacher?" Kailash told about the behavior of general students towards him:

All other students show well behavior to me. But some of them in the general classroom are bad, not following my instructions. I don't give any punishment to them. The head teacher treats them. In some of the places, people give little value to the learning of

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special needs children like visually impaired children. The visually impaired persons have to feel disrespected by the community members. This situation shows the exclusion of visually impaired children from contributing the learning acquired to the development of community and society. Kailash had not felt bad treatment from his friends at school when he was a student but he had heard misbehave to some of the visually impaired students from other general students. Kailash expressed his dissatisfaction with some of his general students that they don't follow his instructions and the head-teacher has to treat them.

Cooc (2019) had argued that the inclusion of children with disabilities into general classroom affects the time spent on instruction as well as the time spent on classroom management by teachers. Cooc's argument in this context matched to Kailash's saying. Not following the instructions of Kailash by some students in the general classroom indirectly gives the meaning that more time is spent on classroom management.

All the above discussions have proved that there is misbehavior at school and exclusion from contributing the learning acquired to the development of community and society to some extent.

Separate classroom potential and the benefits of inclusive class

Due to the special types of problems and needs, the preliminary learning up to the development of basic writing and mathematical skills, a separate classroom is suitable according to this study. In such classrooms, the children can get a suitable environment for their learning. Visually impaired students need wide spaces in classrooms than other general students because of the lack of eyesight. We can manage a limited number of students in such classes.

In answering my question about potential and shortcomings of separate and inclusive class, Kailash expressed his experience as: There are some advantages to a separate classroom in preliminary learning. In such a classroom, we can pay special attention to our special problems. For example, we can't learn the subject matters of mathematics in the general classroom with others. Our script is different from others. These types of matters must be taught us separately. But there are some disadvantages also. Our world will be narrower, we can't learn and feel others' habits and cultures, etc. We have to be weak in out-knowledge.

In the preliminary stage, the visually impaired children have to identify the letters and numbers. They have to learn how to write on brail script and how to do simple mathematical operations. Their writing script doesn't match with the writing script of general students. In this condition, teaching them separately is appropriate. The statement of Kailash represents that matter.

As Gilmour (2018) citing Fuchs et al. (2015) had argued that the math achievement gap between students with or at risk for disabilities and without disabilities in the regular classroom setting was twice as large as the gap in the first group, it is appropriate to manage separate class for visually impaired students for at least the preliminary learning and for the subject matters of mathematics.

After developing the preliminary skills of writing and simple mathematical operation, the common or inclusive classes are appropriate. There are so many benefits of inclusive classroom towards special needs children and for other children also. If a separate classroom is managed, the special needs children can't learn and feel others' habits and cultures. They can't make adjustments with others. But the special needs students can have participatory and cooperative learning in the inclusive classroom. They can learn and feel all these matters in an inclusive classroom. Kailash again added for my previous question:

When we were included in the general classroom with other general friends in grade three, I felt too much happy. We were 9 or 10 only up to grade two. But after inclusion in grade three, we became so many. We played all together. We quarreled all together. I felt so much fun. We had shared and eaten our breakfast altogether. We paid too much attention to the classroom instructions of the teachers, but I was confused at the beginning whether the other students were visually impaired like me or not. Anyway, we had adjusted with too many friends. We had learned how to be adjusted in a congested classroom where there are so many desks and benches. We had learned so many behavioral matters. We had learned other's habits and cultures.

As Ypinazar and Pagliano (2004) argued that inclusive education accepts and values all students and welcomes the diversity they bring to the classroom, Kailash enjoyed the inclusive classroom too much at grade three. He became happy in playing and quarreling with many friends and sharing breakfast with them. Not only that, he learned the habits and cultures of other students slowly.

Hornby, 2011 citing Warnock, 2005 had said that separate special needs placement is wrong because a key goal of education should be to fully include children in the community in which they live. Therefore, they ought to be included in their local mainstream schools. The meaning of Hornby's claim is that for developing the capacity of inclusion in the community, the special needs children must be included in mainstream schools and mainstream classes first of all.

Hornby had claimed again that inclusion in the community after leaving school is the most important end that educators should be seeking. Inclusion in mainstream schools may be a mean to that end but should not be an end in itself.

ICT can be boon

Inclusive classrooms or inclusion in the classroom is so much advantageous to visually impaired children. They can feel the wider world when they moved from a separate classroom to an inclusive one. It can be a great achievement. Despite this fact, the preliminary learning is being operated in a separate classroom in Nepal. The reason is because of the different learning capacity and different scripts, it will be easier to teach them in a separate classroom for developing basic writing and other skills. This means, if we can develop skills by using different technology and equipment in the inclusive classroom that will be better.

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In response to the question "Can modern technology help the learning of visually impaired person?" Kailas said:

Modern technology must be used in the teaching-learning process of visually impaired children. Nowadays stylus and slates are rarely used in developed countries. They use laptops, touchable display boards connected with laptops, and other modern tools for teaching-learning. The typing and printing using braille script are also developed nowadays. Audio typing and audiobooks are also available. These instruments and technologies are not available in remote areas like ours, although they can boost up our knowledge and capacity. The procedures of information communication technologies have to focus on producing instructional materials for visually impaired children.

Information Communication Technology can be a boon for visually impaired children for learning. If this technology can be used in all areas and all educational institutions for the teaching and learning process, inclusion will be more effective.

Eligi and Mwantimwa (2017) citing Olukotun (2004) had argued that technology has impacted positively on the lives of persons with disabilities concerning information use, education, and lifelong learning. It would not only expand the world of the visually impaired students, it can serve as a great equalizer. This concept matches with the idea of Kailash. So, ICT can be a boon for the education of visually impaired children.

CONCLUSION

This article has explored the concept and condition of inclusion for the education of visually impaired children. Visually impaired children basically face problems in maintaining life prospects needed for learning. Kailash had also faced measurable condition during childhood. For Kailash, the learning couldn't be meaningful due to the cause of the lack of learning materials and a limited number of teachers. The mainstream school of nearby community denied admitting Kailash due to the lack of learning materials and trained teachers. This means the management of meaningful inclusion of visually impaired children is yet to be done in Nepalese community schools. For visually impaired children, the preliminary education like understanding the concept of the script, writing letters, and numbers in that script, learning of mathematical processes is difficult and challenging. Therefore, there is the practice of conducting preliminary education in separate classrooms in Nepal. After some grades, moving such students to the inclusive classroom with other general students is in practice. The students face some problems at the beginning stage of inclusion but just after some time, they feel the wider world there. The children can share their feelings, cultures, and attitudes. They learn how to be adjusted with other general friends. The inclusion of a visually impaired student in mainstream schools and mainstream classrooms can support them for developing the capacities for inclusion in the whole society.

Inclusive classrooms from the beginning of formal education can also be useful if we can use the boon of information communication technology for learning of the visually impaired children. Braille display, braille printer, braille note-taker can be used as modern types of equipment for making effective learning of visually impaired students.

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